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Mastery-Of- Subject-Matter and Choice of Instructional Strategy as Correlates of Achievement in Physics among Secondary School Students in Taraba State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explored physics teachers' mastery of subject matter and instructional strategies as correlate to students' academic achievement in Taraba state, Nigeria. Two research questions were raised and two hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The study adopted correlational research design. The population of the study was 17,210 respondents comprised of 84 physics teachers and 17,126 SSIII physics students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Taraba state. A sample size of 460, made up of 69 physics teachers and 391 SSIII physics students of private and public senior secondary schools in Taraba state were selected using purposive and simple random sampling techniques. The instruments used for data collection were Physics Teachers' Knowledge of Subject Matter (Content) Test (PTKSMT), Physics Teachers' Knowledge of Instructional Strategies Questionnaire (PTKISQ) and Physics Achievement Proforma (PAP), with reliability coefficients of 0.79 for (PTKSMT) computed using K-R₂₀ and 0.77 for (PTKISQ) computed using Cronbach alpha. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while the hypotheses were tested using regression analysis at 0.05 significance level. The study generated the following findings: (i) among others revealed that there is a significant relationship between physics teachers' knowledge of the subject matter and students' academic achievement in Taraba state with [F(1, 68) = 164.544, P < 0.05)] and (ii) there is a significant relationship between physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies and senior secondary school students' academic achievement in Taraba state with [F (1, 390) = 179.994, p < 0.05)]. The study concludes that physics teachers' knowledge of the subject matter, physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies and students' academic achievement are positively related. The study recommended among others that Physics teachers content knowledge should be improved through teacher's constant training and re-training on content knowledge.

Keywords. Teachers Mastery, Subject Matter, Instructional Strategies, Academic achievement

Introduction

Science is universally recognized as the foundation of technological development worldwide. In today's modern world, every aspect of life depends on science, and nations, particularly developing countries like Nigeria, are striving to advance technologically and scientifically. It is well understood that any nation aspiring for greatness and development must heavily invest in science education (Ogunsanya & Otedola, 2018). Developed countries such as Germany, China, the United States of America (USA), Japan, the United Kingdom, Russia, and France have gained global recognition and superpower status due to their strong commitment to science education and research (Otache, 2021). Therefore, science education is crucial for any country aiming to achieve sustainable development and compete in the global arena. Among the various branches of science, physics stands out due to its critical role in scientific and technological advancements (Adegoke, 2017). Physics, as one of the major science subjects, plays an important role in the scientific and technological development of the world. It comprises the study of matter, energy, and their interactions. Physics has an important impact on the average person's daily life because it

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helps us to understand various natural phenomena that are embedded in reality. Physics plays a role in nearly every daily activity we perform, such as walking, cutting, watching, and opening or closing things. Many electronic gadgets utilized in homes, schools, industries, hospitals, and even around the entire globe came as a result of ideas, theories, principles, and laws of physics. There is no doubt that, Physics as a branch of science played an indispensable role in the economic development of the world. Yusuf, Omosewo, Akanbi, Mohammed, Badmus, and Usman (2021) affirmed that physics is the basis for most modern technology, tools and instruments used in scientific research development. It provides quantitative and qualitative skills needed for analyzing data and solving problems in sciences, engineering and medicine, as well as in economics, finance, management, law and public policy. Therefore, it is crucial to ensure that students gain high levels of academic achievement in physics.

Despite the significant role of physics and its recognition in science education, its remains a subject in which senior secondary school students in Nigeria continue to perform below the standard benchmark. Education stakeholders, particularly those in the science field, have expressed deep concerns about this situation (Shamim, Tabasum, & Rashid, 2013). Furthermore, Mukama (2019) reported that there is a decline in the number of students enrolled in physics and their academic achievement in schools has consistently been poor over the years. This concerning trend is observable in external examinations such as the West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examinations Council (NECO). The West African Examination Council (WAEC) conducted a seven-year analysis of physics students' results from 2016 to 2022 in Taraba State, Nigeria presented in Table 1. In 2016, the failure rate was 55.49%, 57.19% in 2017, 45.75% in 2018, 50.19% in 2019, 55.35% in 2020, 49.22% in 2021, and 49.83% in 2022 (Taraba State Ministry of Education, Research and Statistics Department, 2023).

Table 1: WAEC Results in Physics in Taraba State from 2016 TO 2022

Year	Pass Rate (%) at A1 - C6	Failure Rate (%)
2016	44.51%	55.49%
2017	42.81%	57.19%
2018	54.25%	45.75%
2019	49.81%	50.19%
2020	44.65%	55.35%
2021	50.78%	49.22%
2022	50.17%	49.83%

Despite the fluctuations in the results, all the failure rates are notably high, with none falling below 45%. This suggests a persistent problem of academic achievement in physics among students in Taraba State. This trend of poor academic achievement of physics students in Taraba State may be attributed to the lack of physics teachers' mastery of subject matter and instructional strategies. Academic achievement refers to individuals' success and performance in educational endeavors. It is a crucial indicator of students' understanding and proficiency in teaching and learning a subject. In the context of physics, academic achievement involves students' success and performance in studying and understanding the principles, theories, and application of physics. According to Filgona, Sakiyo, and Gwany (2020), academic achievement is determined by students' test scores, representing the outcome of education and indicating how well students perform in a specific area of study. However, achieving high academic performance is influenced by various factors, which include not only the students' efforts and abilities but also the roles and contributions of teachers, parents, and educational policies.

Odumosu, Olisama, and Fasayo (2018) affirmed that various stakeholders, including teachers, students, parents, and the Ministry of Education, contributed to the significant decline in academic achievement among physics students in secondary schools based on their related factors. However, Kimani, Kara, and Njagi (2014) submitted that teacher-related factors contributing to poor academic achievement include negative attitudes towards work, ineffective teaching methods, insufficient pedagogical content knowledge, inadequate teacher evaluations, lack of qualifications, and poor rapport with students. Consequently, Tsholofelo and Maree (2021) highlighted student-related factors contributing to poor academic achievement as negative attitudes towards learning, socioeconomic backgrounds, misunderstanding of the content being taught, ineffective study habits, knowledge of the subject matter and poor physical well-being. These combined factors create significant challenges to academic success in subjects such as physics.

Mastery of subject matter refers to teachers' deep understanding of the content they aim to teach or have prepared to impart to students (Hernboom & Mazaring, 2021). It includes knowing the subject's key concepts, theories, laws, principles, its underlying structure, and applications in teaching the subject. For example, if a physics teacher plans to teach students how

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to calculate velocity, then velocity becomes the subject matter (Lumantao, 2022). This means teachers' knowledge of the subject matter may have effect on students' academic achievement. According to Jobeen (2014), teachers with a thorough grasp of their subject can provide clear and accurate explanations, this helps students to grasp complex concepts more easily, reducing confusion and misunderstandings. In recent research done by Denbel (2023) found that the overall subject matter knowledge competency of the teachers has significance influence on students' academic achievement of senior secondary schools in republic of Indonesia. In addition, Olasehinde, Williams, Yahaya and Owolabi (2018) reported that pedagogical and subject content knowledge of teachers were found to be significant predictors of students' academic achievement. However, Gulled (2021) discovered that teacher subject matter knowledge has no effect on students' academic success in Hargeisa district public secondary schools. Based on these conflicting results from different researchers it becomes imperative to study this sub variable more.

Mastery of instructional strategies is a fundamental component of effective teaching (Francisco & Celon, 2020). This knowledge can help educators to deliver lessons effectively and capture students' attention during the learning process. Baafi (2020) defined instructional strategies as various techniques, methods, approaches, and tools that teachers use to facilitate teaching and learning. This aspect of Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) can significantly influence students' academic achievement, as evidenced by several researchers. According to Amos, Folasayo, and Oluwatoyin (2015), teachers who are proficient in various instructional strategies can use different methods to keep lessons interesting and engaging. For example, incorporating interactive activities, discussions, and multimedia makes learning more dynamic and enjoyable for students. These varied approaches not only capture students' attention but also cater to different learning styles, making it easier for students to understand and retain complex concepts.

Freeman, Eddy, McDonough, Smith, Okoroafor, Jordt, and Wenderoth (2014) affirmed that active instructional strategies, which involve students' hands-on activities and collaborative projects, significantly improve student performance in science. In the same vein, Sarfraz, Vladut, Cioca and Ivascu (2022) found that motivational and instructional strategies significantly affect the self-efficacy of teachers and the academic performance of students. However, Ida and Calmer (2015) reported that a student-centered instructional strategy has a negative impact on academic achievement in general. While some studies, affirmed that active and motivational instructional strategies significantly improve student performance, others reported negative impacts from student-centered methods on students' academic achievement. Therefore, the sub variable needs further investigation to understand this nuance. The findings from this study revealed that most of the teachers' methods of teaching have a great effect on students' academic performance; based on these findings, Student-Centered Method and Teacher-Student Interactive Method were recommended in order to improve students' academic performance. Isa and Bala (2022) revealed that most teachers' methods of teaching have a great effect on students' academic performance. Considering the fact that some studies have established that pedagogical content knowledge influences students' academic achievement, while others have found no such correlation, further investigation is necessary to determine the extent to which physics teacher's pedagogical content knowledge relate with students' academic achievement of senior secondary school in Taraba State.

Statement of the Research Problem

In an ideal situation, students studying physics in senior secondary schools in Taraba state would consistently achieve academic success with at least a credit pass in physics. Physics as a fundamental subject would serves as a gateway to numerous promising prospects leading to admission into university and other tertiary institutions to study courses such as medicine, pharmacy, engineering among others. However, despite concerted efforts by scholars and educators, poor academic achievement in physics persists among senior secondary school students in Taraba state with an average percentage failure rate of 51.86% recorded from 2016 to 2022. In addition, students consistently performed below expected standards, indicating a significant gap in their understanding of physics concepts. Various factors, such as teacher qualifications, classroom conditions, instructional resources, and student attitudes towards learning physics, have been implicated in contributing to this issue. Nevertheless, factors that may be contributing to poor academic achievement in Taraba state could be lack of physics teachers' mastery of subject matter and instructional strategies. Students may struggle to grasp physics concepts due to ineffective teaching and lack of depth in teachers' understanding of both the subject matter and how to use appropriate teaching strategies. To address the persistent problem of poor academic achievement in physics among senior secondary school students in Taraba state, this study investigated the correlation between physics teachers' mastery of subject matter, instructional strategies and students' academic achievement.

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Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine the relationship between physics teachers' mastery of subject matter, instructional strategies and students' academic achievement in Taraba state, Nigeria. Specifically, the study determined the:

1. Relationship between Physics teachers' mastery of subject matter (content) and academic achievement among senior secondary school students in Taraba state.
2. Relationship between physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies and academic achievement among senior secondary school students in Taraba state.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions.

1. What is the extent of mean score achievement of Physics teachers' mastery of subject matter among senior secondary schools in Taraba state?
2. What is the response level of physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies among senior secondary schools in Taraba state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' knowledge of subject matter and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary schools students in Taraba state

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers' mastery of instructional strategies and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary schools students in Taraba state

Methodology

The study employed correlational survey research design in determining the relationship between physics teachers' knowledge of subject matter, instructional strategies and students' academic achievement. The population of the study consists of 17,210 physics teachers and students. This includes 84 physics teachers and 17,126 SSIII physics students 2023/2024 academic section from both private and public science secondary schools in Taraba state. The sample size for the study comprised 460. This includes 69 physics teachers and 391 SSIII physics students of private and public senior secondary schools in Taraba state. Purposive, stratified and random sampling was used to draw the sample for physics teachers and physics students in each education zone. Purposive sampling technique was used to select schools from the 10 education zones based on the availability of physics teachers. Three instruments were used for data collection. The instruments include Physics Teachers' Knowledge of Subject Matter (Content) Test (PTKSMT), Physics Teachers' Knowledge of Instructional Strategies Questionnaire (PTKISQ) and Physics Achievement Proforma (PAP). PTKSMT contains 50 items multiple-choice objectives test with four options (A-D) covering senior secondary school Physics curriculum. The 50 items were drawn from past WAEC questions (2015-2022). Each correctly answered item scored 1 mark making the total of 50 marks. For physics teacher's knowledge of instructional strategies questionnaire PTKISQ, the instrument was adapted from Yusuf et al. (2021). The items were slightly modified based on the inputs of the validators to suit the purpose of this study.

Three experts participated in the Content Validation of Physics Teachers' Knowledge of Subject Matter (content) Test (PTKSMT). These experts represented distinct perspectives, with one from the Physics Department Moddibo Adama University, Yola, another from the Department of Physical Sciences Education in the same university, and a third from Taraba State University Demonstration Secondary School, Jalingo. The reliability of the Physics Teacher's Knowledge of Subject Matter Test was assessed using the Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-R₂₀) coefficient, resulting in a reliability coefficient of 0.79. For physics teacher's knowledge of instructional strategies questionnaire PTKISQ the reliability analysis through Cronbach alpha statistical tool, yielding a commendable score of 0.77. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation to answer research questions. Where linear regression was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. If the P-Value is less than 0.05 the null hypotheses was rejected, otherwise do not reject the hypotheses.

Presentation of Results

Research Question One

What is the extent of mean score achievement of Physics teachers' mastery of subject matter among senior secondary schools in Taraba state?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Physics Teachers' mastery of Subject Matter in Senior Secondary Schools in Taraba State

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Variable	N	Mean	S. D
Physics teachers' knowledge of Subject matter	69	35.72	5.21

Key: n= Number of participants, S.D = Standard deviation

Table 1 shows that the mean score for physics teachers' knowledge of subject matter in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is 35.72 and standard deviation is 5.21. This indicates that physics teachers' knowledge of subject matter in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is generally low. On average, their subject matter knowledge level is insufficient to meet the minimum required standard, as indicated by the failure grade (F9).

Research Question Two

What is the Response level of physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies among senior secondary schools in Taraba State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Level of Physics Teachers' Mastery of Instructional Strategies in Senior Secondary Schools in Taraba State

S/N	Item (n = 391)	Mean	S. D	Remark
1	I easily understand the solutions my teacher provides on physics problems in class	4.40	1.53	HL
2	My teacher often uses diagrams to help us understand what he is teaching in physics.	3.44	1.37	ML
3	Physics teacher uses practical examples to teach physics concepts in my school.	3.32	1.42	ML
4	Physics teacher in my school conducts experiments to deepen our understanding of scientific principles	4.33	1.43	HL
5	Physics teacher in my school used to break down physics calculations into simple steps for easy understanding.	3.36	1.41	ML
6	Physics teacher in my school tells stories to help us remember key discoveries made by scientists.	3.37	1.44	ML
7	My teacher uses different ways to explain physics concepts.	3.27	1.46	ML
8	Physics teacher engages students in solving problems during lessons.	2.13	1.52	LL
9	Physics teacher used to create room for every student to participate in the class when teaching.	3.30	1.53	ML
Grand Mean		3.44	1.46	ML

Key: n= Number of participants, HL= High Level, ML=Moderate Level, LL= Low Level, S.D = Standard deviation.

Table 2 shows that the grand mean for the level of physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is 3.44, with a standard deviation of 1.46. The mean falls into the real limit of 2.50–3.49 (Moderate Level). This indicates that the level of physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is moderate.

Hypothesis One

There is no Significant Relationship between Physics Teachers' Mastery of Subject Matter and Academic Achievement in Physics among Senior Secondary Schools students in Taraba State

Table 3a: Summary of ANOVA results of Linear Regression for Relationship between Physics Teachers' Mastery of Subject Matter and Students' Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary Schools in Taraba State

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	876.728	1	876.728	164.544	.000 ^b
	Residual	356.991	68	5.328		
	Total	1233.719	69			

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Physics teachers' knowledge of Subject matter

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The result in Table 3a reveals that there is a significant relationship between Physics teachers' mastery of subject matter and students' academic achievement of senior secondary schools in Taraba state with $[F(1, 68) = 164.544, p < 0.05]$. Since the computed p-value (0.00) is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that there is a significant relationship between Physics teachers' mastery of subject matter and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary schools students in Taraba state.

Table 3b: Model Summary of Linear Regression for Relationship between Physics Teachers' Mastery of Subject Matter and Students' Academic Achievement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.843 ^a	.711	.706	2.30830

a. Predictors: (Constant), Physics teachers' knowledge of Subject matter

The result in Tables 3b indicates a model summary of how the independent variable explains the variance in the dependent variable. The result shows there is a significant positive relationship between Physics teachers' mastery of subject matter and students' academic achievement with $R=0.843$ and the adjusted R-square value (.706) indicates that 70.6% of the variance in students' academic achievement is explained by physics teachers' mastery of subject matter.

Table 3c: Beta Coefficient of Linear Regression for Relationship between Physics Teachers' Mastery of Subject Matter and Students' Academic Achievement

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	-1.872	1.938		-.966	.338
	Physics teachers' knowledge of Subject matter	.689	.054	.843	12.827	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic achievement

The result in Table 3c reveals the Beta coefficient of regression analysis. It reveals a significant beta coefficient of 0.843, $p < 0.05$. This indicates that physics teachers' mastery of the subject matter has a strong positive impact on students' academic achievement. This standardized coefficient allows for a comparison of the relative importance of different predictors in the model, indicating that teachers' subject matter mastery is a significant predictor of students' academic success in physics.

Hypothesis Two

There is no Significant Relationship between Physics Teachers' Mastery of Instructional Strategies and Academic Achievement in Physics among Senior Secondary Schools students in Taraba State

Table 4a: Summary of ANOVA results of Linear Regression for Relationship between Physics Teachers' Mastery of Instructional Strategies and Students' Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary Schools in Taraba State

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	26382.095	1	26382.095	179.994	.000 ^b
	Residual	57016.429	389	146.572		
	Total	83398.523	390			

a. Dependent Variable: Students' academic achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies

The result of linear regression in Table 4a shows that $[F(1, 389) = 179.994, p < .05]$. Since the computed p-value (0.00) is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected suggesting that there is indeed a significant relationship between Physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies and academic achievement in Physics among senior secondary schools students in Taraba state.

Table 4b: Model Summary of Linear Regression for Relationship between Physics Teachers' Mastery of Instructional Strategies and Students' Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary Schools in Taraba State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.562 ^a	.316	.315	12.10668

a Predictor: (Constant), Physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies

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Table 4b indicates that there is moderate positive relationship between Physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies and students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Taraba state as shown by the R-value of 0.562 and the adjusted R-square value (.315). This suggests that, 31.5% of variance in students' academic achievement can be explained by the predictor variable (Physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies) in the model.

Table 4c: Beta Coefficient of Linear Regression for relationship between Physics Teachers’ Mastery of Instructional Strategies and Students’ Academic Achievement

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	18.217	1.907	9.554	.000	
	Physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies	7.223	.538	.562	13.416	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Students’ academic achievement

Table 4c shows results of Beta coefficient of regression analysis. it reveals a significant Beta coefficient of $\beta = 0.562$, $p < 0.05$. This indicates that Physics teachers' mastery of instructional strategies has a significant positive effect on students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Taraba state.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the study revealed that the mean score achievement of physics teachers' knowledge of subject matter in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is generally low. On average, physics teachers’ subject matter knowledge is insufficient to meet the minimum required standard, as indicated by fail grade (F9), and that there is a significant relationship between Physics teachers' knowledge of the subject matter and students' academic achievement in Taraba state. This finding agrees with that of Olasehinde, Williams, Yahaya and Owolabi (2018), Adu and Olatundun (2017), Denbel (2023), Sadiq (2019), Njoroge and Githua (2018) who found that there is significant relationship between teachers’ knowledge of subject matter and student’s academic achievement at the end of their studies. However, this finding disagrees with that of Baumert et al (2020), Gulled (2021) who found that teachers’ subject matter knowledge has no effect on students' academic achievement. It could be inferred from the study that teachers' knowledge of the subject matter translates to enhanced academic achievement of students.

The study also found that the level of physics teachers’ knowledge of instructional strategies in senior secondary schools in Taraba State is moderate with a mean of 3.44. In addition, there is a significant relationship between physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies and senior secondary school students' academic achievement in Taraba state. This finding aligns with Baafi (2020) and Onweh and Udeme (2015), who reported that the use of effective instructional strategies had a significant impact on students' academic performance. According to them, when teachers employed diverse instructional methods, such as interactive lectures, group work, and practical activities, students demonstrated higher levels of understanding and improved academic performance. However, this finding disagrees with Pianta, Hamre, and Allen (2015), who found that there is no significant impact of teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies on student achievement. Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that physics teachers' knowledge of instructional strategies significantly contributes to improving the academic achievement of students studying physics. This highlights the importance of equipping teachers with diverse and effective teaching methods to foster better learning outcomes.

Conclusion

The study revealed significant relationship between physics teachers’ mastery of subject matter and instructional strategies on students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Taraba State. These emphasize the critical role of teachers' expertise in influencing students’ outcomes. Therefore, the researcher concluded that physics teachers’ mastery of subject matter and instructional strategies significantly relate to students’ academic achievement in physics. This means that a positive or negative change in a teacher’s knowledge of subject matter and instructional strategies will result in a corresponding shift in the academic achievement of students.

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Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. Since there is significant relationship between Physics teachers' content knowledge and students' academic achievement, physics teachers content knowledge should be improved through teacher's constant training and re-training on content knowledge.
2. To further improve students' academic achievement in Physics in senior secondary schools in Taraba state, it is recommended that Physics teachers undergo continuous training and professional development programmes like workshop focusing on instructional strategies. This will enable them to employ a variety of effective teaching techniques that cater to diverse learning styles as well as expose them to the latest teaching approaches and facilitate better understanding among students.

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